

Dual-fuel characteristics of a lean azimuthal flame (LEAF) combustor

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Abstract

Lean azimuthal flame (LEAF) is a recently introduced novel combustion concept that aims to bring down emissions from aviation [1]. Dual-fuel operations of the LEAF combustor presented in this work comprised simultaneous injections of jet A-1 and hydrogen accompanied by opposed air crossflow. An axisymmetric combustor houses three pairs of a straight spray flame and an inclined hydrogen flame at equidistance in circumference. Each of these pairs is entrained by a hot vitiated flow (mixture of combustion products and opposed fresh air) such that it ignites the next pair to maintain sequential combustion. This rapid interaction constituted a toroidal reaction zone and hence lean azimuthal flame. This study evaluated the potential of operating LEAF combustor under a wide range of operating conditions. Different combustion regimes are identified by varying thermal power, changing spray properties in terms of atomization-air to liquid mass flow ratio (ALR), altering the strength of toroidal motion with variable opposed air mass flow, and for two different chamber lengths. The stability of LEAF configuration and its transition into tubular flame is studied through simultaneous high-speed OH* chemiluminescence imaging and measurement of chamber pressure fluctuation. Results of OH* chemiluminescence analysis showed the topological variation of LEAF with thermal power and with chamber length. The regime of stable LEAF is identified and explained. Moreover, the transient LEAF behavior is also captured and described in this paper.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of LEAF combustor, (b) bottom fuel manifold (BFM) showing the liquid and gaseous fuels injection arrangement, and (c) top air manifold (TAM) composed of 12 numbers of opposed air injection inserts.

The range of operating parameters considered to study LEAF configuration.

Keywords: Azimuthal flame; Dual-fuel; Hydrogen; OH* chemiluminescence

Information for Colloquium Chairs and Cochairs, Editors, and Reviewers

1) Novelty and Significance Statement

The results presented in this paper are novel in terms of identifying the regime of stable and transient LEAF. Explaining transient-LEAF configuration is unique for such a combustion concept. The geometrical changes (chamber length and opposed air diameter) brought down the pressure drop across the chamber to an acceptable level. With this work, the dual-fuel LEAF operation limit is expanded for high thermal power with acceptable pressure drop.

2) Author Contributions

- C. S. Vegad: Paper writing, experiments, data analysis, results interpretation
- O. Birelli Schmid: Experiments, data processing
- K. Pandey: Review and editing, results discussion
- N. Noiray: Designed research, funding acquisition, review and editing, results discussion

3) Authors' Preference and Justification for Mode of Presentation at the Symposium

The authors prefer **PPP** presentation at the Symposium, for the following reasons:

- Novel combustion concept
- Capability of dual-fuel operations
- Futuristic sustainable aviation technology

1. Introduction

The global climate crisis we are facing today is the consequence of the rise in emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases (GHGs). The sources of emissions are spread across the different sectors. Over the past few decades, the aviation sector has contributed about 4 % of world CO₂ emissions [2]. It is challenging to achieve net-zero emissions aviation as it relies on energy-dense liquid hydrocarbons. A short-term and most viable solution that achieves ultra-low emissions is the use of alternative fuels and innovative sustainable aviation technologies. The present research work characterizes the new combustion concept called lean azimuthal flame for a wide range of dual-fuel (jet A-1 and hydrogen) operations.

In the development of clean combustion for aviation, the LEAF concept studied here is the mixing of hot products with the reactants increasing their temperature prior to combustion. It is a flameless oxidation with a distributed reaction zone [3]. LEAF concept was first tested for the methane [4], for hydrogen [5, 6], and it was also tested for kerosene at different atomization characteristics [7, 8]. They found LEAF topology is difficult to sustain for kerosene spray of large droplets at low atomization air-to-liquid ratio. However, this concern is rectified by adding a small amount of hydrogen simultaneously with liquid fuel [1]. It has also increased the LEAF operating limit. Moreover, with hydrogen injection, it is possible to operate at a lower equivalence ratio and thus reduce the NO_x and CO emissions [9].

Dual-fuel operations considered in the present work involved the multiphase flow in complex environment of distributed reaction zone which limits the work reported in available literature. In the recent studies [1, 8], a high-pressure drop across the chamber was noted. In order to reduce the pressure at an acceptable level, one of the objectives of the present work is to reduce pressure drop by geometric adaptation. The new combustor configuration is then characterized for dual-fuel capability for a wide range of operating conditions. The regimes of stable and unstable LEAF at different operating parameters are determined. The transient-LEAF at high thermal power is evaluated for the first time in this paper.

2. Experimental configuration

LEAF combustor configuration and operating conditions are explained at the beginning of this section. Which is followed by a description of the measurements and optical diagnostics techniques.

2.1. LEAF combustor

Lean azimuthal flame combustion chamber is shown schematically in Fig. 1. It is an axisymmetric configuration with a hexagonal arrangement of quartz windows as an outer wall. The design allows to vary

the length of the combustion chamber (L_{CC}) by adjusting the distance between the fuel injection manifold (FIM) and air injection manifold (AIM), see Fig. 1a. FIM accommodates three liquid and three gaseous fuel ports at equidistance in the chamber circumference. In the present study, the jet A-1 sprays were injected axially (Z -direction) using air-blast atomizers (Delavan, SN30610-1), while the hydrogen gas was injected at 57° through 3 mm diameter ports. The arrangement of the fuel injection is shown in Fig. 1b. Note the location of the igniter is at the center of the FIM. The air injection, as an oxidizer, is opposite to the fuel through AIM at L_{CC} downstream location. It is called opposed air (OA) that combines twelve air jets that emerged at 45° from 2.5 mm diameter air inserts of AIM.

The combustion products of jet A-1 and hydrogen mixture are entrained by the opposed air creating a hot vitiated crossflow in the vicinity of FIM. This hot vitiated crossflow ignites the next pair to maintain sequential combustion. The rapid interaction across the mixture flames constitutes a toroidal reaction zone and hence lean azimuthal flame (LEAF) configuration. The venting of hot gases is taking place through the central exhaust arrangement (Fig. 1a).

2.2. Operating conditions and optical diagnostics

The potential of operating LEAF combustor for a wide range of operating conditions is evaluated. The volume of the combustion chamber is also varied by changing its length. Two different chamber lengths of $L_{CC} = 60$ mm and 80 mm are studied for a range of jet A-1 thermal power (5-35 kW) by keeping constant thermal power of hydrogen as 1.2 kW. The influence of spray properties is evaluated in terms of atomization-air to liquid mass flow ratio (ALR). Three different ALR ratios of 2, 3, and 4 are considered in the current study. The global equivalence ratio (ϕ_{global}) is maintained lean in the range of $0.4 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$.

To quantify the required momentum of opposed air that sustains LEAF configuration, the fuel-to-air momentum flux ratio, MFR is presented. It is the ratio of the total momentum flux of jet A-1 sprays (q_{spray}) and hydrogen jets (q_{H_2}) to the momentum flux of opposed air (q_{OA}),

$$MFR = (q_{spray} + q_{H_2})/q_{OA} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$q_{spray} = \frac{\rho_{jA1} A_{jA1} u_{jA1}^2 + \rho_{AA} A_{AA} u_{AA}^2}{A_{spray}}$$

$$q_{H_2} = \rho_{H_2} u_{H_2}^2$$

$$q_{OA} = \rho_{OA} u_{OA}^2$$

The quantities ρ and u respectively are the density and velocity of jet A-1 ($jA1$), atomization air (AA), hydrogen gas (H_2) and opposed air (OA). A_{spray} is

Fig. 1: Schematic of LEAF combustor showing; (a) fuel injection manifold (FIM), air injection manifold (AIM), and toroidal reaction zone. The hot gases are exhausted from the central exhaust of AIM. The length of the chamber (L_{CC}) in the Z -direction in isometric view; (b) arrangement of air-blast atomizers, hydrogen injection ports, and igniter.

Table 1: Operating conditions for two different chamber lengths.

OC#	L_{CC} [mm]	$P_{jet A-1}$ [kW]	H_2 [kW]	ALR [-]	ϕ_{global} [-]	MFR [-]
1	60	7-35	1.2	2	$0.45 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	20-94
2	60	5-35	1.2	3	$0.40 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	25-200
3	60	5-35	1.2	4	$0.40 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	35-400
4	80	7-35	1.2	2	$0.45 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	20-84
5	80	5-35	1.2	3	$0.40 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	25-200
6	80	7-35	1.2	4	$0.60 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$	35-280

1 the cross-sectional area at the spray orifice, it is a
 2 total of jet A-1 and atomization air areas at an atomizer
 3 orifice. The range of operating conditions for two dif-
 4 ferent chamber lengths is provided in Table 1. All the
 5 operations are carried out at atmospheric conditions,
 6 and without any preheating of fuel and air.

Fig. 2: (a) Cross-section view of LEAF combustor showing pressure measurement locations. (b) Schematic of OH^* chemiluminescence arrangement. The direction of rotation of is clockwise, and thus note the position of the camera capturing the entrainment of hydrogen towards the spray flame.

7 The pressure fluctuation in the combustor is
 8 recorded using the piezoelectric pressure sensors
 9 (Kistler, 601CBA, 0-7 bar, linearity $\leq 1\%$ at FSO).

10 The acquisition system (NI-9234 and cDAQ-9178)
 11 was set at a 50 kHz rate for 10 seconds. The loca-
 12 tions of two sensors (p'_1 and p'_2) are seen in the sketch
 13 of the LEAF combustor cross-section in Fig. 2a. The
 14 static pressure of the combustion chamber (P_{CC}) and
 15 opposed air (P_{OA}) are measured using pressure trans-
 16 mitters (Sensorox DT-V-0-6, ceramic sensor, 4-20
 17 mA, 0 to 6 bar, stability $\leq 0.2\%$) at two down-
 18 stream locations of fuel injection. The flame topology
 19 was studied through OH^* chemiluminescence high-speed
 20 imaging at 10 kHz. The optical arrangement of OH^*
 21 chemiluminescence is shown in Fig. 2b. The high-
 22 speed camera (Photron, FASTCAM SA-X2, 12 bit,
 23 1024x1024 pixels at 12500 fps) is positioned to vi-
 24 sualize through one of the quartz windows of LEAF
 25 combustor. The incoming signals are intensified with
 26 the help of a high-speed intensifier (HS-IRO, LaVi-
 27 sion; IV Generation). Since the primary emission of
 28 OH^* is at about 309 nm, a UV lens (Cerco, 100 mm,
 29 f2.8, $T \leq 90\%$) with a bandpass filter (Chroma, $T \leq$
 30 70% at 310 nm, FWHM 10 nm) is placed in front of
 31 the intensifier.

3. Results and discussion

33 LEAF combustor is characterize for dual-fuel opera-
 34 tions of a wide range of operating conditions (Ta-
 35 ble 1). The influence of chamber length and spray
 36 characteristics on the pressure drop across the cham-
 37 ber is presented at the beginning, which is followed
 38 by the LEAF extinction limit. Next, the variation in
 39 LEAF topology at low to high thermal powers is ex-
 40 plained based on the high-speed OH^* chemilumines-
 41 cence imaging analysis. In the end, transient LEAF
 42 behaviour at high power is explained.

Fig. 3: Pressure drop across combustion chamber for the operating conditions $OC1-6$ of Table 1 is plotted in (a)-(f), respectively. The contours represent the LEAF configuration at various ϕ_{global} . The upper edge of the contour is the LEAF extinction limit.

3.1. Pressure drop across the combustor

The pressure drop across the combustor (ΔP) is quantified to investigate the effect of geometrical change. In the present work, pressure drop is defined as the difference between opposed air injection pressure (P_{OA}) and chamber pressure (P_{CC}), see their locations in Fig. 2a. The percentage of pressure drop across the chamber is given by

$$\Delta P(\%) = (P_{OA} - P_{CC})/P_{OA} \times 100. \quad (2)$$

Figure 3 shows the variation of $\Delta P(\%)$ with change in total thermal power ($P_{th} = P_{jetA-1} + P_{H_2}$). The relations plotted in Figs. 3a to 3f are corresponding to $OC1$ to $OC6$ of Table 1.

The contours represent the global equivalence ratios at which LEAF topology is established. A linear increment in pressure drop with thermal power is noted for each ϕ_{global} in all cases. For a fixed P_{th} , the rise in ΔP is also noticed when ϕ_{global} is varied from near the unity to very lean conditions ($\phi_{global} \approx 0.4$). The reason is an increase the opposed air flow rate till the flame or LEAF blows out. As a consequence of access air in the chamber making ϕ_{global} lean and P_{OA} high in equation (2). This is why the lowest ϕ_{global} in all the contours represents the extinction limit in Fig. 3. The LEAF topology and hence flame goes off immediately if the opposed air increases beyond this limit. The reason could be too much momentum than what is required for holding the toroidal

reaction zone. However, on the other side of the contours, where $\phi_{global} \approx 1$, the LEAF topology holds for all the cases. LEAF topology is also observed for rich equivalence ratios $\phi_{global} \geq 1$, but presenting here is beyond the scope of this paper.

The contours of ALR-2 ($OC1$ and $OC4$) indicate chamber length has not much influence on ΔP . At lower thermal power, in the order of 10 kW, instead of a toroidal reaction zone, the individual spray flames were observed for $0.8 \leq \phi_{global} < 1$. Perhaps the opposed air momentum is not sufficient and hence $\Delta P < 5\%$ for these cases (see Figs. 4a and 4d). However, the toroidal reaction zone is achieved even at lower thermal power in the case of $\phi_{global} < 0.8$. If we focused on higher thermal power ($P_{th} \geq 25$ kW), it was difficult to hold the LEAF for ALR-2 and $\phi_{global} < 0.8$. This happened because of the large SMD of jet A-1 at ALR-2 leading to poor mixing [8]. Further, the momentum of opposed air in the case of $\phi_{global} < 0.8$ is such that the convection time scale of jet A-1 droplets is larger than the evaporation time scale responsible for discontinuation from LEAF topology [8].

Nevertheless, for ALR-3 at $P_{th} \geq 25$ kW, the smaller droplets hold the LEAF even for $\phi_{global} < 0.8$, as shown in Figs. 4b and 4e. Regarding ALR-4, it was difficult to sustain LEAF for a wide range of ϕ_{global} in the case of 80 mm chamber length, as compared to 60 mm (Figs. 4c and 4f). The possible reason could be the increased momentum of opposed

1 air strong enough to blow off the flame.

2 To determine the influence of spray characteristics
 3 on pressure loss, the variation of ΔP with P_{th} for
 4 three different ALRs at a constant equivalence ratio,
 5 $\phi_{global} = 0.8 \pm 0.02$ is plotted in Fig. 4. The high-
 6 est ΔP is reached for ALR-2 as compared to ALR-3
 7 and 4 for both chamber lengths (Figs. 4a and 4b).
 8 Reduction in ΔP with high ALR is due to additional
 9 atomization air resulting in higher chamber pressure.
 10 Moreover, to maintain the global equivalence ratio
 11 constant (as plotted for $\phi_{global} = 0.8 \pm 0.02$ in Fig. 4),
 12 the amount of opposed air has to reduce to compen-
 13 sate for additional atomization air.

Fig. 4: The variation of pressure drop across the combustion chamber for the constant $\phi_{global} = 0.8 \pm 0.01$ and three different ALRs at chamber lengths (a) 60 mm and (b) 80 mm. The marker in (b) is pressure loss obtained by Miniero et al. [1] for 1.9 mm diameter of opposed air inserts (d_{OA}), which is 2.5 mm in the present study.

14 To see the effect of increasing opposed air in-
 15 serts diameter (d_{OA}) on combustor pressure drop,
 16 the current result is compared with previous work by
 17 Miniero et al. [1] in Fig. 4b. They noticed about
 18 20% pressure drop at 25 kW thermal power for 80
 19 mm chamber length. They suspect it is because of the
 20 higher momentum of opposed air jets that emerged
 21 from $d_{OA} = 1.9$ mm diameter inserts. However, in
 22 the present study, the pressure drop is reduced to al-
 23 most half $\Delta P \approx 10\%$ for the same thermal power
 24 and chamber length, but with the increased diameter
 25 of inserts as $d_{OA} = 2.5$ mm (Fig. 4b).

26 3.2. LEAF extinction limit

27 LEAF topology is obtained for the lean ϕ_{global}
 28 close to unity for the given P_{th} . As explained, ϕ_{global}
 29 is then kept on reducing by increasing opposed air
 30 till the flame goes off. As a consequence, an entire
 31 toroidal reaction zone moves towards the fuel in-
 32 jection but with strong azimuthal momentum. There-
 33 fore, the spray flames started from their source of con-
 34 tinuous fresh jet A-1 supply and this is how extinction
 35 happens. It is the fight between momentum arising
 36 from FIM and AIM.

37 Figure 5 presents the LEAF extinction limit for the
 38 lowest ϕ_{global} at corresponding P_{th} . The extinction
 39 limit is noted towards very lean for lower thermal
 40 power. For example, in Figs. 5 and 5b, the LEAF
 41 can sustain for $\phi_{global} \leq 0.6$ when operating at for
 42 $P_{th} \leq 10$ kW. For this range, the momentum of op-
 43 posed air is comparatively higher, which is clear from
 44 the subset plots of $1/MFR$ in Fig. 5. To evaluate
 45 how chamber length affects the extinction, consider
 46 ALR-4 for $P_{th} \leq 25$ kW in Fig. 5. At $L_{CC} = 60$
 47 mm, LEAF extinction happens at lower ϕ_{global} in the
 48 case of ALR-4 as compared to ALR-2 and 3. How-
 49 ever, at $L_{CC} = 80$ mm, extinction for ALR-4 is at
 50 higher ϕ_{global} compared other ALRs. The possible
 51 reason could be the longer distance that opposed air
 52 to travel for 80 mm length with higher momentum
 53 as compared to 60 mm, see subset plots of ALR-4 in
 54 Figs. 5a and 5b. At very high thermal power, $P_{th} >$
 55 25 kW, the extinction limit does not follow the same
 56 trend for both the length and all ALRs. Interestingly,
 57 it is observed that LEAF established up to very lower
 58 ϕ_{global} for very high P_{th} . However, some of the tran-
 59 sient LEAF mechanisms are also observed while oper-
 60 ating in this regime, and also explain in the present
 61 study.

62 3.3. Stable LEAF

63 Based on the outcome of a wide range of operat-
 64 ing conditions, the regime for stable LEAF is speci-
 65 fied. However, there are transient cases also observed.
 66 To characterize LEAF in these regimes, simultane-
 67 ous high-speed OH^* chemiluminescence imaging and
 68 pressure fluctuations within the chamber were carried
 69 out. Even though it is possible to operate LEAF at
 70 ALR-2 with the addition of hydrogen [1], ALR-3 and
 71 4 are considered for further analysis.

72 LEAF topology for low and high thermal powers
 73 are shown in Fig. 6. To see the variations with power
 74 and chamber lengths, the global equivalence ratio,
 75 $\phi_{global} = 0.8 \pm 0.01$ and ALR-4 constant. At low
 76 thermal power ($P_{th} \leq 10$ kW), a clear trace of hy-
 77 drogen flames communicating to jet A-1 spray flames
 78 is observed for both lengths. The flames are close to
 79 the fuel injection with a small lift-off height. Three
 80 spray flames with minor inclination in the azimuthal
 81 direction are noticed due to the weak toroidal reac-
 82 tion zone. Such inclination is less in $L_{CC} = 80$ mm

Fig. 5: LEAF extinction at lean ϕ_{global} for (a) OC# 1-3 and (b) OC# 4-6. The subset plots are the variation of $1/MFR$ corresponding to extinction.

1 as compared to 60 mm because of less penetration of
 2 low momentum opposed air.

3 For intermediate power ($P_{th} = 20$ kW), an en-
 4 trainment of hydrogen and jet A-1 spray in a strong
 5 toroidal reaction zone established a complete LEAF
 6 topology (Fig. 6). The jet A-1 spray flame lift-off
 7 is more compared to the low-power case. Similar to
 8 what is explained earlier, at 60 mm chamber length,
 9 an adequate penetration of opposed air by entrain-
 10 ing hot products results in a fully established LEAF.
 11 While, at 80 mm, the spray flame penetration in the
 12 longitudinal direction is seen for 20 kW power in
 13 Fig. 6.

14 At high thermal power, the reaction zone is ob-
 15 served to be lifted more from the fuel injection man-
 16 ifold, as shown for $P_{th} = 35$ kW in Fig. 6. A strong
 17 reaction zone promoting an efficient mixing results in
 18 uniform LEAF configuration, in particular at $L_{CC} =$
 19 60 mm (Fig. 6).

20 3.4. Transient LEAF

21 A rapid morphological transition of LEAF to tubu-
 22 lar flame and forming back the LEAF is referred to
 23 as transient LEAF in the present study. This kind
 24 of behavior is observed for some operating condi-
 25 tions while reducing ϕ_{global} with opposed air incre-
 26 ment. Figure 7 demonstrates the occurrence of tran-

Fig. 6: Time-averaged OH^* chemiluminescence images showing LEAF topology varying with low to high thermal powers for $L_{CC} = 60$ mm (left) and 80 mm (right) at constant $\phi_{global} = 0.8 \pm 0.01$ and ALR-4. The intensity of OH^* (I_{OH^*}) is normalized between 0 to 1.

27 sient LEAF for $\phi_{global} = 0.7$ and 30 kW thermal
 28 power at 60 mm chamber length.

29 This phenomenon is captured in OH^* chemilumi-
 30 nescence with simultaneous measurement of chamber
 31 pressure fluctuations. The integrated intensity of OH^*
 32 for each image is subtracted by mean and plotted in
 33 Fig. 7a. While corresponding pressure fluctuation is
 34 shown in Fig. 7b. The instantaneous OH^* chemilu-
 35 minescence images showing the morphological transi-
 36 tion at different time stamps is shown in Fig. 7c.

37 The time window chosen for the transient LEAF is
 38 marked in Fig. 7b. The peak of p' and I_{OH^*} in both
 39 the plots are indication of complete LEAF configura-
 40 tion, corresponding to pressure fluctuations (i' and p')
 41 marked in Fig. 7b. LEAF at 242 ms is detached from
 42 the continuity and transformed into a tubular flame
 43 (at 320 ms in Fig. 7c). The tubular flame stayed for
 44 a while and immediately reattached to the fuel injec-
 45 tion forming a LEAF. This complete cycle of transient
 46 LEAF finished within 170 ms.

47 4. Conclusions

48 Dual-fuel characterization of a LEAF combustor
 49 for a wide range of operating conditions is evaluated
 50 in this paper. The reduction of pressure drop across
 51 the chamber is achieved by increasing the size of op-
 52 posed air injection port. On the basis of chamber
 53 length, study suggests a 60 mm chamber length is
 54 suitable stable LEAF for wide range of equivalence
 55 ratio. However, at 80 mm chamber length and ALR-4,
 56 it was difficult to sustain LEAF for the equivalence ra-

Fig. 7: Transient behaviour of LEAF at $P_{th} = 30$ kW and $\phi_{global} = 0.7$ for 60 mm chamber length. (a) Intensity fluctuation I'_{OH^*} is the integrated intensity of each OH^* chemiluminescence image subtracted by mean. (b) Pressure fluctuation (p') within the chamber. (c) Instantaneous OH^* chemiluminescence images showing a sequence of morphological transitions of LEAF configuration at different time stamps within the time window marked in (b).

1 tio below 0.8. The transient behavior at high thermal
 2 power and lower equivalence ratio is also observed
 3 and explained. The transient LEAF described in this
 4 paper opens the perspective of instability study for the
 5 LEAF concept.

6 Declaration of competing interest

7 The authors have no known competing financial inter-
 8 ests or personal relationships that could have appear-
 9 ed to influence the work reported in this paper.

10 Acknowledgments

11 The research work presented in this paper was
 12 performed within the framework of FFLECS project
 13 funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe
 14 research and Innovation programme under Grant
 15 Agreement No 101096436. Views and opinions
 16 expressed are however those of the author(s) only
 17 and do not necessarily reflect those of the European
 18 Union. Neither the European Union nor the grant-
 19 ing authority can be held responsible for them. ETH
 20 Zurich (Switzerland) participants in Horizon Europe
 21 Project FFLECS are supported by the State Secre-
 22 tariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)
 23 Nr. 23.00512.

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